

Privacy Preservation in Textual Data: A Systematic Mapping Study on Differential Privacy and Semantic Similarity

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Selection Criteria - Study Quality Assessment Criteria Although the exclusion criteria help identify relevant studies, it remains interesting to apply a quality assessment checklist to check that the selected practices are methodologically sound and that their impacts have been evaluated. To this end, we employed the following checklist as a basis for including studies in our review, where each paper will be assessed based on the criteria in Table 1:

Table 1. Quality Assessment Criteria (QAC)

QAC	Criteria
QAC-1	Relevance to semantic, rarity, or privacy dimensions.
QAC-2	Clarity of methodology.
QAC-3	Reproducibility of experiments.
QAC-4	Presence of quantitative evaluation.
QAC-5	Novelty or innovation in the applied methods